

Dissolving Probability Theory's Bertrand Paradox by Correctly Accounting for the Sample Space

Sriram Vajapeyam

Eeksha Research
Bangalore, India

sriram@eeksha.com
v.sriram.blr@gmail.com

February 2026

Abstract

The very foundations of probability theory appear to be shaken by the 1889-stated, so-deemed Bertrand Paradox, which is still deemed – more than a century later in 2026 – to allow multiple correct solutions to the posed probability problem depending upon which solution approach is taken. While for the limited purposes of pedagogy there is consensus on which proposed solution is the best one, all of the proposed different solutions are still considered correct. Probability theory, being a man-made model of events unlike the actual physical behaviour of quantum mechanics, would perhaps be better off not allowing multiple solutions if it is to be fully useful. Prior attempts at resolving the paradox have appealed to the principle of indifference and the principle of maximum entropy in their quest for a resolution that satisfies the properties of scale invariance, translational invariance, and rotational invariance but have not yielded a successful resolution. In this article we dissolve this so-deemed paradox itself by leveraging the very basics of probability theory. Working from first principles, we show that correctly accounting for the fundamental factor of sample space in the probability calculation yields exactly one correct solution to the problem and thus dissolves the paradox. To correctly account for the sample space, we first recognise that there are two valid interpretations of the problem: real, physical geometry and idealised geometry interpretations. The idealised geometry interpretation yields continuous distributions and infinite spaces along with their counting difficulties – a confounding factor that has contributed to this problem being perceived thus far as a paradox. We address this issue by calculating probabilities for the two different interpretations using the two separate, respectively appropriate methods of set theory and measure theory. Further, when the limitations of the model of ideal geometry result in it not providing sufficient information for probability decisions we invoke the principle of universal solution with its concomitant property of interpretational invariance to obtain the required information from the underlying real, physical model. With this careful accounting of the sample space, we show that only one of the originally proposed solutions is correct – for both interpretations – while the other two proposed solutions fail for both interpretations of the problem due to their incorrect accounting of the sample space. Thus we dissolve the Bertrand paradox with a careful accounting of the sample space using a first-principles approach to the problem. The Bertrand Paradox having originally been stated in a set of lecture notes published as a book, this article is written in the style of a primer such that even a beginner student of probability can easily follow the explanations.

1. Introduction

In probability theory a problem posed by Bertrand over a century ago in 1889 [Bert1889][BertXlat25] continues to be perceived as a paradox in 2026 [WikiBert][Jaynes1973][LaOd1981][Alon2015][ShRo2019][Kaus2022]

[Sieg2022][Shac2024][Ryan2025]. This probability problem supposedly allows multiple “correct” solutions, with no universally-applicable principle or method successfully proposed so far for picking one correct solution amongst them. This quandary raises questions about the applicability and/or correct usage of probability theory itself in modelling both similar artificially-posed problems and natural events. Bertrand states in his book of lecture notes [Bert1889],

“This paradox shows that the *Calculus of Probabilities* requires a precise definition of the conditions under which chances are evaluated, otherwise the results are indeterminate.”,

thus bringing into question the very basis, applicability, and extent of usefulness of probability theory.

In this article we will show that the very so-deemed paradox itself does not exist in the first place: the problem lies in wrong accounting of the problem’s sample space in the proposed solutions, compounded by limitations of the ideal geometric model of the problem space. The paradox gets dissolved by careful analysis of the proposed solutions.

An English translation of the problem posed by Bertrand[Bert1889], as provided by chatGPT (*Appendix A*) and semantically equivalent to that used in prior research, is:

“A chord is drawn at random in a circle; what is the probability that it is longer than the side of the equilateral triangle inscribed in this circle?” (see Figure 1).

The basic solution approach would be to count the number of chords in the circle, viz., the *sample space*, count the number of chords that satisfy the stated requirement, viz., the *event space*, and then take their appropriate ratio to obtain the required probability. The supposed paradox emerges from the methods used to uniquely determine chords and then to count them. Bertrand proposes three different approaches to determining the chords in his original paper [Bert1889][BertXlat25], and these result in three different probability values being computed:

- i. the chord is determined by its two **endpoints**, so the chords are counted by counting unique end-point pairs. This results in the probability being determined to be **1/3**;
- ii. the chord is determined by choosing a radius at random and then selecting a point at random on this radius as the **midpoint** of the chord, the chord being perpendicular to the radius at this point. This results in the probability being determined to be **1/2**;
- iii. the chord is determined by choosing a point at random within the circle and drawing the chord through this point, **perpendicular** to the line from the center to the point. This results in the probability being determined to be **1/4**.

To reiterate, two fundamental aspects underlie all the above solutions: (i) a method for determining chords, and (ii) a method for counting chords. We will examine the chord-determining methods in the appropriate sections of this article. With regard to counting chords, notice that the above solutions determine chords by selecting points that lie on or within the circle, so chords are counted by counting those points. Thus, counting points is an integral part of all three proposed solutions above. However, the original paper does not explicitly address the question of whether the points assumed in the solution are *idealised geometric concepts* having zero dimension (with lines, arcs and the circle correspondingly being one-dimensional; termed *Euclidean geometry*) or real-world two-dimensional points (as would then be lines, arcs, and circles) as implicitly assumed in some of the subsequent proposed resolutions of the paradox. For example, [Jaynes1973] proposes that a machine throw a rain of straws onto a circle to get a random sampling of chords (which would be the segments of the straws that end up lying on and within the circle). This basic assumption about the geometry of the points has direct bearing on the solution because idealised points are accounted for in a

Figure 1. A circle with an equilateral triangle XYZ inscribed. Chord XM is shorter than the triangle's side XY; chord XN is longer.

manner different from real points, as seen in the difference between *set theory* [Levy1934] and *measure theory* [Tao2012][Rosen2006] and explained in the appropriate sections of this article.

Attempts at resolving the paradox such as [Jaynes1973][Sieg2022][Shac2024][Ryan2025][Kaus2022], some of which assume real points as opposed to idealised points, fail to handle either ideal points or even real points themselves correctly [Alon2015][ShRo2019]. Some of these solutions appeal to guiding principles such as the *principle of indifference* [Lap1814/1995:6-7] which consists “*in reducing all the events of the same kind to a certain number of cases equally possible, that is to say, to such as we may be equally undecided about in regard to their existence*” but which is known to run into its own paradoxes [Shac2024]. This principle is then replaced with the *principle of maximum entropy* [Jaynes68] which states that “*the prior probability assignment should be the one with the maximum entropy consistent with the prior knowledge*” [Jaynes1968:229] where the entropy mentioned is Shannon entropy [Vaja2014]. This principle too runs into its own paradoxes [ShRo2019]. These prior approaches attempt to find a resolution that satisfies the properties of *scale invariance*, *translational invariance*, and *rotational invariance*. However, all these approaches are shown to fail to meet the goal, instead creating their own paradoxes [ShRo2019]. In this article we do not delve into these and other prior attempts at resolving the paradox.

Working from first principles, we will show in this article that only the end points solution (i) above is valid in all respects, for both idealised points and real points; it satisfies the *principle of universal solution* and thus has the property of *interpretational invariance*. Solution (ii) fails because it does not correctly account for the case of real points, though it unwittingly handles the case of idealised points ambiguously. Solution (iii) fails for both real and idealised points on account of not handling an end case correctly.

This article is organised as follows. We start with an elaborate discussion of the implications of the choice of real and idealised points for the problem in section 2, explaining as a primer the problems with counting infinite sets of ideal points. In section 3 we work through the correct end-points based solution, first for real points and then for idealised points. In section 4 we first point out the error in the second proposed solution (ii) for real points, and then argue that, while its solution for ideal points is ambiguous, it is not the appropriate choice since it does not generalise to real points. This is the crucial argument for how to handle infinite sample spaces; we propose the *principle of universal solution* that is concomitant with the property of *interpretational invariance*. In section 5 we point out the error of the third proposed solution (iii) in handling an end case of the sample space, for both real and idealised points. Section 6 summarises the analysis of the different proposed solutions and draws conclusions regarding the pitfalls in properly accounting for the sample space and event space in these probability calculations.

2. Problem Interpretation: Physical vs. Idealised Geometry

There are two ways of interpreting Bertrand's problem: is the circle mentioned in the problem (and therefore its chords):

- i. a physical, real circle drawn say with a pencil on paper or with pixels on a screen?
- ii. a virtual, imagined circle having geometrically idealised points that are of zero length, area, and volume?

The two interpretations have different impact on how points, and thereby chords, are counted, thus affecting the calculation of the desired probability. Indeed, they have a fundamental impact on what is countable and what is not. In this article, we will consider both interpretations when solving the problem and when pointing out the errors in the proposed but wrong solutions. We now discuss in detail the implications of these two assumptions for the problem solution.

2.1 *Physical interpretation.*

For the *physical interpretation* we assume that the circle alluded to in the problem statement is drawn with *real, physical* points that have a *non-zero* physical dimension, contrasting with the theory of geometry which considers a point to be dimensionless, i.e., of zero length, area, and volume. One of the smallest real points we can pragmatically think of is a hydrogen atom, so we visualise a 2-D projection of the hydrogen atom – which would be a circle of a certain small radius – as the smallest possible point. We first draw the circle in Bertrand's problem with these points.

Next, chords are also assumed to be drawn with similar points, and we assume that chords can begin and end only on the centres of these points that lie on the circle's circumference (in particular, chords cannot end in-between the centres of two adjacent points on the circumference). We can think of this as "quantization" of the circle – there are a *finite* number of points on the circle's circumference, each point is itself a circle of a *finite* radius, and the end points of the chords of the circle can *only be* these finite number of points on the circumference.

Note that we start by actually drawing the circle alluded to in the problem statement on say a graph paper having x and y axes drawn on it – this means that the points of this particular circle's circumference occupy specific (x,y) coordinates on the graph paper. Now the space within the circle is empty, so chords drawn with real points can occupy any interior part of the circle and also criss-cross over each other anywhere, but they can only end on the centres of the already-drawn points of the circle's circumference. Without loss of generality, the probability computed for this circle, which is one of many such circles, will apply to any other such physical circle drawn. The difference between different drawn physical circles of the same centre and radius would be the differences in (x,y) coordinates of corresponding points – if the first circle's first point was at say (r,0), the second circle's first point could be slightly offset from it while still staying on the same circle, e.g., at ((r – delta), epsilon) but still on the circle, but not offset by so much as to completely overlap with the corresponding second point of the first circle. The probability calculation for this second circle will be no different – we can simply rotate that circle to overlap with the first circle and then the solution will be the same. So the solution will be *rotation-invariant*. The solution will also be *scale-invariant* because we do not assume any particular length for the radius of either the circle or the points. The solution will also be *translation-invariant* since we do not rely on, i.e., take into account, where on the graph the circle is located. Thus the solution will be a general solution for real, physical circles.

2.2 *Idealised geometry interpretation.*

In the *idealised geometry interpretation*, a point is an imaginary, idealised, dimensionless thing that has zero length, width, and height, unlike the hydrogen atom's 2D circle projection that we visualised as being a point in the physical interpretation. These idealised points thus also occupy zero area and volume. The idealised lines drawn with these idealised points are also imaginary, having just one dimension, the length, and no thickness or width or volume. How a one-dimensional line is drawn with points of zero dimension is left to the imagination! Zero dimensions and the transition from zero dimensions to one dimension is indeed just an abstract model; all models come with limitations because they are only models, not the real things that they model.

This idealisation affects the counting of the points and of the chords, because with such infinitesimal points there will be an *infinite* number of points on any length of line, just as there are an infinite number of real numbers between say just the adjacent integers 0 and 1 on the real-number line.

2.2.1 *Infinite Points on any Line Segment*

To understand this, consider two supposedly adjacent real numbers 1.23456 and 1.23457. We can always find a new real number in-between any such pair of numbers by appending a digit to end of the first number, e.g., 1.234568. Since we can keep appending any number of digits like this, there is no end to this process and hence there are an infinite number of real numbers between even 0 and 1.

Now suppose we want to come up with the smallest *non-zero* real number ρ that approximates the zero length of an idealised point. Let us say we start with 0.000001: after the decimal point, five zeros followed by a 1. We can make this number ρ as small as we wish by adding any number of zeros immediately after the decimal point and before the 1, e.g., 0.00000000001, after the decimal point there being ten zeroes followed by a 1. Next, we can consider the idealised points, i.e., circles, to be placed touching each other on the real-number line, starting with their centres at 0, ρ , 2ρ , 3ρ , 4ρ and so on until 1, as the points have length (diameter) ρ and thus occupy length ρ on the real-number line. Those real numbers now represent those points, and counting those real numbers amounts to counting the number of those points between 0 and 1. Since there is no end to making ρ smaller, there is no end to the number of such ρ -length points that occupy the real-number line between 0 and 1. In the limit, as ρ approaches zero, the number of points on the line of length 1 (between 0 and 1) approaches infinity, as the count becomes the number of real-numbers between zero and 1, which is infinite.

2.2.2 Counting difficulties with infinite points

These zeroes and infinities bring with them their counting difficulties, making the calculation of the probability tricky, requiring that pitfalls be avoided.

From here on, once p is zero and the point is idealised, all the difficulties with counting the number of real numbers in any portion of the real-number line apply to counting the number of points on a line of corresponding length. For example, we can map every real number between 0 and 2 to a real number between 0 and 1 by dividing that number by 2, so there are at least as many real numbers between 0 and 1 as between 0 and 2! This translates to there being as many idealised points on a line of length 1 as on a line of length 2! Given any two real-number line segments, the numbers on the larger segment can be mapped onto numbers of the smaller segment by dividing them by a suitable ratio and adding/subtracting an offset. For example, every real number between 10 and 17 can be mapped onto real numbers between 1 and 3 by first subtracting 10 (to map them on to 0-7), then dividing by $(17-10)/(3-1) = 3.5$ to map them on to 0-2, and then adding 1 to shift them to between 1 and 3. This translates to there being at least as many idealised points on a line or arc of length 2 as on a line or arc of length 7, if we start counting them individually! Generalising this, half the circumference (say) of a circle will have at least as many idealised points on it as the entire circumference. The same holds for areas as well: all the idealised points within the circle can be mapped on to idealised points within a quadrant, i.e., a quarter of the circle! Thus, with idealised points, there are an infinity of them in any line, area, or volume and so the concept of counting them all breaks down.

Further, to get a feel for how equating measures such as length and area to a count of the number of idealised points in them is simply not valid, consider equating the area of the circle to the number of points within it, counted as follows. Suppose we say that the number of points on a radius is proportional to its length r . Each radius is defined by two endpoints, the circle's centre (which is common to all the radii) and the radius' endpoint on the circumference. Counting all the radii then amounts to counting all the points on the circumference, which can similarly be incorrectly considered to be proportional to its length $2\pi r$. Then if the circle's area is considered to be proportional to the number of points in it, we can calculate that to be $r(2\pi r) = 2\pi r^2$, double the circle's actual area!

2.2.3 Probability Calculations with Infinite Points

Now let us look at probability calculations for these situations where the *sample size*, i.e., the number of different possible outcomes for any trial, is infinity. Suppose we randomly pick a real number r between 0 and 1. The probability that r is exactly 0.723, say, is zero! That is because 0.723 is one of the infinite numbers between 0 and 1, so the probability of picking that number is one in infinity, i.e., $1/\infty$, which is 0. Thus the probability of picking any particular number or point out of an infinity of such numbers or points is zero! So then, how do we go about calculating any sort of probabilities in this situation?

Notice that the probability $p(0,1)$ that r lies between 0 and 1 is still, by definition, 1. This is despite the fact that, by the normal definition of probability, that probability $p(0,1)$ has to be the sum of the probabilities of each of the numbers r_i between 0 and 1, $\sum p(r_i)$, but those probabilities $p(r_i)$ are all zero! This paradox arises because we cannot count or always sum up an infinite number of numbers; though, there are infinite series of non-zero real numbers that sum up to a number.

To overcome the above problem, in the probability calculation here we completely avoid counting individual numbers, points, etc. when they belong to an infinite set of such things. Instead, we calculate probabilities for outcomes falling in a range of the sample space. Let us start with the probability $p(0,1)$ that r lies between 0 and 1 being 1 by definition. Because the real numbers are distributed between 0 and 1 it must be the case that $p(0,1) = p(0, 0.5) + p(0.5, 1) (= 1)$. Further, since there is no difference in the distribution of real numbers in (0,0.5) and (0.5,1), we must have $p(0, 0.5) = p(0.5, 1) = 0.5$. We can continue subdividing the ranges and repeating the argument, e.g., (0, 0.5) consists of (0, 0.25) and (0.25, 0.5), and so on. We can repeat this so long as each range has more than a single idealised point of size zero and probability zero, thus avoiding the difficulties with zeroes and infinities. By these arguments, we end up with the fact that the probability of r being on a sub-segment of the real-numbers line between 0 and 1 is proportional to the length of that sub-segment. For example, the probability r that it is greater than half, i.e., $0.5 < r \leq 1$, is $(1-0.5)/(1-$

$0) = 0.5$. While the two real-number line sub-segments $[0,1]$ and $[0.5,1]$ both have an infinite number of real-numbers on them, as we just discussed, we have avoided counting those points and used the ranges or lengths of those sub-segments instead. The length of a real-number line sub-segment, or any line, is called its **measure**, as are areas and volumes of other geometric or mathematical objects. There is an entire mathematical theory around measures, naturally named **measure theory** [Tao2012], and around analysing such infinite sets as real numbers, again naturally named **real analysis** [Rudin1970]. In fact, probability theory has been extended from discrete sample spaces to encompass continuous sample spaces using measure theory [Rosen2006]!

Thus we see that there are pitfalls in counting individual points, and thus individual chords, in the idealised geometry interpretation of the Bertrand problem – we will have to deal with them carefully and differently. Chords in the idealised geometry still do terminate on points on the circumference, and still do have a midpoint (and are perpendicular to the radius that goes through their midpoint), just that there are an infinite number of such points now. This makes the direct counting of individual chords impossible in the probability calculations, so we will have to use other methods of probability calculation based on ranges.

In this rest of this article, for each of the evaluated solutions we will first deal with the physical interpretation and then the idealised geometry interpretation.

3. The Correct End-Points Solution

The first solution proposed by Bertrand [BertXlat25] determines chords as follows:

“the chord is determined by its two endpoints... fix one endpoint, say point A, and let the second endpoint B vary along the circumference.”

Implementing Bertrand’s first proposed solution to his so-deemed paradox, in order to draw the first chord we pick one real, physical point at random on the circle as its starting point. The other end of the chord can now be any of the other points on the circle’s circumference. If the radius of the circle is r and the diameter of our real point is d , we can calculate the length l that the point occupies on the circumference (it will be greater than d ; the calculation is left to the reader as an exercise). So now the circumference has $(2*\pi*r)/l$ points including the first randomly selected point. We allow a chord from the first point to itself, of length zero, to simplify the explanation; the reader is encouraged to repeat the solution without this allowance. So, given the randomly chosen first point, $(2*\pi*r)/l$ chords can be drawn starting from it.

Of these, how many chords are greater than the side of the equilateral triangle that can be inscribed in the circle? Now visualise that equilateral triangle with two of its sides starting out from the same chosen random point X (Figure 1), making that point a vertex of the triangle. Looking at the geometry of the equilateral triangle XYZ and the circle, it is clear that the three arcs of the circle over the three sides of the equilateral triangle are all equal in length because the corresponding sides are equal and at the same distance from the circle’s centre. Now, only the chords that go to points on the arc $arcYZ$ over the side YZ opposite to the chosen random point X will be longer than the side of the equilateral triangle. To see this in a simple way, visualise walking along the circumference from the chosen point X , drawing chords back to the starting point from the current position. The chord length starts out very small (close to X) and continuously increases until the point diametrically opposite to the starting point is reached. Along the way, when the point Y on the side of the equilateral triangle is reached, the chord length becomes equal to the triangle’s side, and subsequently it becomes greater. We can do the same exercise on the other side of the original chosen point as well. This makes it clear that only the chords that end on the arc over the triangle’s side YZ that is opposite to the starting point X are longer than the triangle’s side. But that arc $arcYZ$ accounts for $1/3$ rd of all points on the circle, as the other two arcs are of equal length and they account for $1/3$ rd each as well. Thus, given a randomly chosen first point X for a chord, the probability that the chord drawn from there will be greater than the side of the equilateral triangle is $1/3$.

Next, the starting point of the chord could actually be any of the points on the circle. But for each such choice, by symmetry, the probability of the chord being longer than the equilateral triangle’s side remains the same, $1/3$: you can rotate the circle so that the new point aligns with the earlier point X , and then the problem is exactly the same as earlier. Once we have thus allowed the starting point of the chord to be any point on the circle and the chord’s end to be any other point on the circle, we have accounted for every possible chord -- though not just once but twice! For any

Dissolving Bertrand's Paradox

chord AB, there is no difference between it being drawn from A to B and from B to A. Thus each chord AB is counted twice: once when A is chosen as the starting point, and once when B is chosen as the starting point, with both being guaranteed to be chosen thus by the method used. However, this double counting of chords does not affect the probability because both the longer chords and the shorter chords are counted twice, resulting in both the numerator and denominator of the probability formula getting multiplied by two:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\text{chord longer than side}) &= (\text{size of event space})/(\text{size of sample space}) \\ &= (\text{number of longer chords})/(\text{total number of all chords}) \\ &= (2*\text{number of longer chords})/(2*\text{total number of all chords}) \\ &= (2 * (2*\pi*r/l)*1/3) / (2 * (2*\pi*r/l)) \\ &= 1/3 \end{aligned}$$

This solution meets the basic requirement that the *sample space*, i.e., all the chords, and the *event space*, i.e., all the longer chords, are both fully and correctly accounted for, thus proving the result.

3.1 Idealised Geometry End Points

Consider both points and the chords themselves to now be idealised as discussed in section 2.1. The measure 'l' in the denominator of the formula $(2*\pi*r/l)$ above -- being the portion of the circumference occupied by an individual point -- now becomes zero. Therefore the above formula evaluates to infinity, resulting in difficulty in counting the number of points on the circumference. As discussed in detail in section 2.1, we can sidestep this counting problem by using the fact that all the three arcs arcXY, arcXZ, and arcYZ of Figure 1 are of equal length and part of the same circumference, as follows.

Suppose we draw a chord at random, best visualised as dropping on top of the idealised circle an idealised one-dimensional straw made up of idealised points and of length greater than the diameter of the circle, and then cutting off the portions of the straw that extend outside the circle. Let us take one end of the resultant chord, a point X on the circumference, to be a given. This is without loss of generality because that one end of the chord could have fallen on any point of the circumference. Now, given this one end point X (Figure 1 again), the other end point of the chord could have fallen on any of the three arcs of the circumference, arcXY, arcYZ, or arcXZ. Only the chords ending on arcYZ are longer than the side of the equilateral triangle. Based on the discussion in section 2.1, we can calculate the probability of the second endpoint falling on arcYZ to be $\text{length}(\text{arcYZ})/\text{length}(\text{circumference}) = 1/3$. This applies to all chords, no matter what point on the circumference is chosen as the first endpoint of the chord, because of the symmetry inherent in the circumference -- the circle can always be rotated to align the first point with X to apply the same calculation. Thus, we have accounted for the entire sample space of chords. So we again get the same probability $1/3$ as the answer for Bertrand's problem, just as we did in the discrete interpretation.

The important trick we have used in the above argument is to sidestep actually counting the number of ideal points in any arc or counting chords by counting their endpoints. We use the lengths of the arcs, called a Lebesgue measure [Tao2012], to essentially argue that the number of chords ending on each of the three arcs of equal length is the same and thus that the probability of the second endpoint landing on arcYZ is $1/3$. In the next sections, we will see that trying to count the number of dimensionless (infinitesimal) points in any length of line, area, or volume, and thereby counting the number of chords, results in pitfalls and wrong solutions.

4. The Incorrect Radial Points Solution

The second solution proposed by Bertrand [BertXlat25] determines chords as follows:

"the chord is determined by choosing a radius at random and then selecting a point at random on this radius as the midpoint of the chord, the chord being perpendicular to the radius at this point."

The probability is then calculated [BertXlat25] using just a single such radius, as follows:

"The chord's length depends on the distance from the center to the midpoint. Let the circle's radius be r. The side of the inscribed equilateral triangle has length $r\sqrt{3}$. A chord with midpoint at distance x from the center has length

$2\sqrt{(r^2-x^2)}$. This chord is longer than $r\sqrt{3}$ if $2\sqrt{(r^2-x^2)} > r\sqrt{3}$, which simplifies to $x < r/2$. Since the midpoint is chosen uniformly along the radius (from 0 to r), the probability that $x < r/2$ is $(r/2)/r = 1/2$. Thus, the probability is $1/2$."

The problem with the above solution is that it implicitly assumes that the chords thus yielded by the points on the chosen random radius are representative of the entire sample space which is all the chords of the circle. Let us carefully examine if this method correctly accounts for the entire sample space -- first for the case of real points and then for idealised points.

For real points, we take their tiny radius, e.g., that of a hydrogen atom as discussed in section 2, to be r_0 . We start by drawing the (points of the) circumference of the original circle of radius r (Figure 2) – the real points P2, P1, P3, etc., lie on the circumference of the circle, with their idealised centres O2, O1, O3, etc., respectively. To fully account for the sample space as counted by the proposed approach, we should systematically cover all the radii of the circle. We can do so by systematically going around the circumference selecting points in sequence one after the other, choosing the radius that connects each point's center to the circle's center. Now all the points on all of these radii together form the sample space as counted by the proposed approach. Whether this sample space corresponds to the sample space of the problem is to be investigated, in order to validate this proposed solution.

First we analyse a single radius. Say we start with the real point P1 on the circle with its idealised centre O1 (Figure 2), then select its radius O-O1 ($=r$), and account for all the points on that radius. To check if those radial points yield all the corresponding chords, we simultaneously analyse the chords using the earlier end-points approach. For this we pick the points P2 and P3 on the circumference adjacent to P1, with their centres at O2 and O3. Observe that the chord O2-O3 connecting these two points should be the next chord accounted for by the proposed radial method, after the zero-length chord O1, because chord O2-O3's centre C lies on the radius O-O1, by the symmetry of triangles O-O1-O2 and O-O1-O3.

By the current radial points solution's method of counting chords, the next point to be picked for chord determination is Pr having centre Or, which is immediately adjacent on that radius to P1 and yields chord MN. Simple visual inspection itself shows that Or and C, the centre of chord O2-O3, are different points: Or is further up towards the centre from O1 than C. This visual inspection result can be backed up with the following calculation. Notice that the two points (i.e., circles) P1 and P2 touch each other at T1 (which is *not* on the circumference), and therefore O2-T1-O1 is straight line – when two same-size circles touch at a point, their respective radii that terminate at the point form a straight line due to symmetry of the two circles. Since both O1 and O2 lie on the circle, O-O1 = O-O2 = r , the circle's radius, and therefore O-O1-O2 is an isosceles triangle. Since O1-T1 = O2-T1 = r_0 , O-T1 is the perpendicular bisector of the triangle's base O1-O2 and is thus tangent to both circles. (By symmetry the same things apply to triangle O-O1-O3.) From the just-prior discussion, O1-O2 = O1-T1 + O2-T1 = $2*r_0$ = O1-O3, r_0 being the radius of a point. So

$$\begin{aligned} O1-C &= (O1-O3)*\sin(O1-O3-C) \\ &= 2*r_0*\sin(O1-O3-C). \end{aligned}$$

However, by definition of P1 and Pr,

$$O1-Or = 2*r_0$$

Since angle O1-C-O3 is a right angle by symmetry, angle O1-O3-C is an acute angle, and so its $\sin()$ is less than 1. Therefore

Figure 2. The radial points method of drawing chords. Points are shown very large; only for purposes of illustration. The two points P1 and Pr (shaded circles) are immediately adjacent to each other on radius O-O1. Points P2 and P3 are immediately adjacent to P1 on the circumference. The second possible chord MN of this method, after the zero-length chord at O1, is perpendicular to the radial point Pr (having centre Or) and misses the next real chord O2-O3. This shows that the radial points method does not fully account for the sample space.

$O1-O_r > O1-C$,

which means that the radial points method misses accounting for the chord O2-O3 as mentioned above.

This immediately proves that the radial points method misses counting the chord O2-O3, as radius O-O1 misses it and no other radius will pass through the midpoint C of this chord. Thus the radial points method does not correctly account for the problem's sample space, and hence is a wrong solution.

Several other chords will also be similarly missed by the radial points method as one proceeds along the radius to the centre of the circle. Without delving into the distribution of the missed chords according to their positions and therefore lengths, we can conclude from the above analysis and the differing answer of this solution compared to the end points solution that the radial points solution is wrong for real, physical circles because it does not correctly count the sample space of the problem.

4.1 Idealised Geometry Radial Points

With idealised points as well, Bertrand's proposed second method runs into trouble on the count that it tries to account for the chords with radii hosting the chord midpoints. While we can use the same argument as in section 3.1 to calculate the probability (being equal to $\frac{1}{2}$) of a randomly chosen chord's midpoint¹ being in the half of the radius closer to the centre and thus the chord being longer than the equilateral triangle's side, there is a sample space paradox with the choice of a radius instead of the circumference.

Suppose we move on the radius O-O1 (Figure 2) from its bottom-most point O1 on the circumference up towards the centre O, constructing chords MN for each radial point. As in the discrete points case, each such chord will have its two end points on the arcs O1-M and O1-N of the two bottom quadrants that are on either side of the radius. As the point on the radius moves upwards towards the centre, the chord end points on the two arcs also move upwards, along the circumference. When the radial point travels distance r to reach the centre, the end points would each have travelled the longer distance of a quarter of the circumference, $\frac{1}{4} * (2 * \pi * r) = \frac{1}{2} * \pi * r$, to reach the horizontal diameter of the circle. But the problem is not just with the travel distance. Along the way to the centre, when the radial point reached the midway point $r/2$, the threshold for chords longer than the equilateral triangle's side, the end points would each have travelled a distance $(\pi * r / 3)$ on the arcs², which is two-thirds of the arc length. This leaves just the smaller distance $(\frac{1}{2} * \pi * r) - (\pi * r / 3) = (\pi * r / 6)$ to be covered by the end points in the remaining half ($r/2$) of the travel of the radial point to the centre. This means that uniform travel of the chord midpoint along the radius does not translate to uniform travel of the chord endpoints on the circumference! Travel of the chord midpoint along a short radial segment can result in travel of the chord endpoints on either longer or shorter arc segments depending on the specific position of the radial segment on the radius. The reverse is also true – uniform travel of the chord end points on the circumference does not result in uniform travel of the chord midpoint on the radius. In the case of real/physical points we saw this behaviour at the level of the individual points. Here in ideal geometry, while we cannot measure or count individual points, we still see the same behaviour at the level of ranges of points, i.e., arc segments and radial segments.

The above paradox leaves us with the question of which segment lengths to take into account in the probability calculation: midpoint travel segments on the radius or the longer endpoint travel segments on the circumference. Further, one can imagine a random, curved path from O1 to O that lies between the radius and the circumference in one of the lower quadrants; the distance covered on this path will be even longer! The question that emerges is: which choice correctly accounts for the sample space and the event space of chords?

We cannot resolve this question of choice by considering individual chords like we did in the physical interpretation. There is no basis to resolve the choice based on individual points given that each ideal point has no dimension, there is no empty space or gap between adjacent ideal points on the radius, the arcs or the curved path, and there are an infinite number of points on all of them. That leaves us the option of considering ranges or distances in this

¹ The point lying on a particular radius and being the point on which the chord is drawn, perpendicular to the radius.

² This simple geometrical calculation is left as an exercise to the reader, with the hint that the radius originating at the chord end point is now at an angle of 60° to the vertical radius

ideal geometry. But then, here again there seems to be no compelling reason to pick either the radius or the arc, or even the random interior curved path, for covering the sample space.

We argue that the above quandary is really a limitation of ideal geometry, which is a man-made abstraction of real, physical geometry: being only a model of a real thing, it does not fully account for or provide information about every aspect of the real thing. The quandary is not a problem with or limitation of probability theory, it is rather a case of the ideal geometry model pulling the sample space rug from under the feet of probability theory by its limitations! In such scenarios, where the limited model does not provide enough information on the basis of which to make a rational decision, we should be guided by the additional information present in the real, physical world that it models. Doing so will allow the solution to work correctly for *both* the real, physical world and for the model. We take this **principle of universal solution**, which leads to **interpretational invariance**, to be a hallmark of a correct solution. If a proposed solution works correctly only in one interpretation of the problem and not in the other, we discard that proposal as not being a universally correct solution.

In keeping with the above *principle of universal solution* for the resolution of quandaries, we take the chord end points into account for covering the sample space even in this ideal interpretation, not their midpoints or any other points. Therefore we use the circumference arcs to account for the chords and their sample spaces, not radii or other random lines or curves. Doing so, if we randomly select two endpoints M and N on the two bottom quadrants such that the chord has its midpoint on the vertical radius O-O1, there is only a 1/3 probability (i.e., not 1/2) of the chord midpoint being within distance $r/2$ from the centre and thus of the chord being longer than the equilateral triangle's side. This is because the length of the circumference arc corresponding to the radial distance 0 to $r/2$ is 1/3rd of the arc length corresponding to the radial distance $r/2$ to r , as discussed earlier. Thus the proposed radial midpoints solution is wrong for idealised geometry as well.

5. The Incorrect Interior Points Solution

The third solution proposed by Bertrand [BertXlat25] determines chords as follows:

“Suppose the chord is determined by choosing a point at random within the circle and drawing the chord through this point, perpendicular to the line from the center to the point.”

The probability is then calculated [Bert1889] using just a single such radius, as follows:

“The chord is longer than the side of the inscribed equilateral triangle ($r\sqrt{3}$) if the point lies within a concentric circle of radius $r/2$. The area of the circle with radius $r/2$ is $\pi(r/2)^2 = \pi r^2 /4$, and the area of the full circle is πr^2 . The probability that a randomly chosen point lies within the smaller circle is the ratio of the areas: $(\pi r^2 /4)/(\pi r^2) = 1/4$. Thus, the probability is 1/4.”

This proposed solution suffers from a very basic problem in accounting for the sample space of chords: the centre of the circle has an infinite number of chords (diameters) passing through it, unlike the other points selected by this method, which will have only one chord each! Also note that all the chords (diameters) passing through the centre will be larger than the side of the equilateral triangle.

The above incorrect accounting of the chords passing through the circle's centre occurs in both the discrete and idealised interpretations of the problem, even if counting of points is incorrectly allowed in the idealised interpretation. Thus this proposed third solution fails in both interpretations for the same reason – incorrect accounting of the sample space.

6. Summary and Conclusions

We have done a careful and detailed analysis of the Bertrand paradox: three supposedly – and paradoxically – correct solutions proposed in [Bert1889][BertXlat25] to the probability problem posed therein. First we identified and proposed that there are *two distinct possible interpretations* of the problem: a real-world, physical geometry interpretation and an idealised Euclidean geometry interpretation. We then provided a *primer on infinite sets*: the difficulties in counting things in the idealised geometry of zero-dimension points and one-dimensional lines. Subsequently we analysed each of the three proposed solutions for both interpretations of the problem. We first showed

Dissolving Bertrand's Paradox

the *end-points based solution* to be correct for both interpretations as it correctly accounts for the sample and event spaces and correctly handles the counting difficulties of idealised geometry. Second, we showed the *radial points based solution* to be wrong for real, physical geometry because it incorrectly accounts for the sample space. For idealised geometry, since there is insufficient information to decide whether this method correctly accounts for the sample space, we introduced the *principle of universal solution* and its concomitant property of *interpretational invariance* to show that the radial points method is wrong for idealised geometry as well. Third, we showed that the *interior points method* is wrong for both problem interpretations since it does not account properly for the centre point of the circle.

Overall, in probability theory the correct calculation of probability rests on correct accounting of the *sample space*, the *outcome space*, and the *event space*. We have shown that such careful accounting has not been done in two of the three proposed solutions due to (i) not considering the two possible interpretations of the problems as physical and idealised geometries, (ii) not calculating probabilities according to the rules of infinite sets (in the case of idealised geometry), and (iii) in one proposed solution, simple oversight of a part of the sample space. That leaves us with just one correct solution to the posed probability problem and thus a completely dissolved paradox.

The main lessons that can be drawn from our careful analysis and dissolution of the Bertrand paradox include:

- i. the need for very careful accounting of the sample space and consequently the event and outcome spaces when calculating probabilities;
- ii. the need to distinguish between discrete and continuous sample spaces in probability calculations, and the need for measure theory [Tao2012] based probability calculations [Rosen2006] when the sample space is continuous;
- iii. when calculating probabilities with limited models of reality that do not provide sufficient information to make decisions, the need to look to the underlying reality for the required additional information;
- iv. when a problem has multiple valid interpretations, the need to adhere to the *principle of universal solution* to obtain a solution that satisfies the property of *interpretational invariance*, *i.e.*, that is valid across all interpretations.

We conclude that this long-standing supposed paradox in probability theory – the Bertrand paradox – is in fact no paradox at all, it just required very careful analysis to be entirely dissolved.

Acknowledgements

Pramod Batni brought the Bertrand Paradox to the attention of the author. He also pointed out an early careless error of logic, as well as provided a sounding board for early explanations of this work.

References

- [Alon2015] Failure and Uses of Jaynes' Principle of Transformation Groups, Alon Drory , Foundations of Physics, Volume 45, Issue 4, pp. 439-460, April 2015. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2015FoPh...45..439D/abstract>
- [Bert1889] Calcul des probabilités, Joseph Bertrand, Gauthier-Villars et fils, Paris, 1889, pp. 1–12. https://www.hist-math.fr/textes/Bertrand1889_CalculProbabilites.pdf
- [BertXlat25] Appendix A, English Translation of [Bert1889] by chatGPT, October 2025. Page 14. <http://www.eeksha.com/resources/bertxlat.pdf>
- [Jaynes1968] Jaynes, E. T. 1968. Prior Probabilities. Systems Science and Cybernetics, IEEE Transactions on, 4, 227-41

- [Jaynes1973] The Well-Posed Problem, Edwin T. Jaynes, Foundations of Physics, 3, (1973), pp. 477-493.
- [Kaus2022] "A New Solution of Bertrand's Paradox", Kaushik, P., Theory of Probability & Its Applications, vol.67, No.1, 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.1137/S0040585X97T990836>
- [LaOd1981] Urban Operations Research, 3.3.2 Bertrand's Paradox, Richard C. Larson and Amedeo R. Odoni, Prentice-Hall, NJ, 1981. https://web.mit.edu/urban_or_book/www/book/chapter3/3.3.2.html
<https://web.mit.edu/tee/www/bertrand/problem.html>
- [Lapl1814] "A Philosophical Essay on Probabilities", Laplace P. S., translated by Emory, F. L. and Truscott, F. W. New York: Dover
- [Levy1934] "Basic Set Theory", Azriel Levy, Berlin ; New York : Springer-Verlag, 1934. Internet Archive:
https://archive.org/details/basicsettheory00levy_0
- [Rosen2006] "A First Look At Rigorous Probability Theory", (2nd Edition), World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd.
<https://turan-edu.uz/media/books/2024/05/28/1664973378.pdf>
- [Rudin1970] "Real and Complex Analysis", Walter Rudin, University of Wisconsin-Madison, 1970. McGraw-Hill Series In Higher Mathematics.
<https://www.mheducation.co.in/real-and-complex-analysis-9789355326119-india>
<https://perso.telecom-paristech.fr/decreuse/downloads/c22155fef582344beb326c1f44f437d2/rudin.pdf>
- [Ryan2025] "Bertrand's Paradox is a Paradox of Infinity", Patrick J. Ryan, 16 July 2025. *Synthese* **206**, 61 (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-025-05140-1>
- [Shac2024] "Bertrand's Paradox and the Principle of Indifference", Nicholas Shackel, 2024. Routledge.
<https://philpapers.org/rec/SHABPA-13>
- [ShRo2019] "Bertrand's Paradox and the Maximum Entropy Principle", Shackel, Nicholas & Rowbottom, Darrell, 2019. Philosophy and Phenomenological Research.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333187445_Bertrand's_Paradox_and_the_Maximum_Entropy_Principle
- [Sieg2022] Probability, Mathematical Statistics, and Stochastic Processes, 10.2: Bertrand's Paradox, Kyle Siegrist, Apr 24, 2022.
[https://stats.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Probability_Theory/Probability_Mathematical_Statistics_and_Stochastic_Processes_\(Siegrist\)/10%3AGeometric_Models/10.02%3ABertrand%27s_Paradox](https://stats.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Probability_Theory/Probability_Mathematical_Statistics_and_Stochastic_Processes_(Siegrist)/10%3AGeometric_Models/10.02%3ABertrand%27s_Paradox)
- [Tao2012] "An Introduction to Measure Theory", Terence Tao, 2012. American Mathematical Society (AMS).
<https://terrytao.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/gsm-126-tao5-measure-book.pdf>
<https://bookstore.ams.org/gsm-126>
- [Vaja2014] "Understanding Shannon's Entropy metric for Information", Sriram Vajapeyam, arXiv, 24 March 2014.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.2061>
The Net Advance of Physics: INFORMATION <https://web.mit.edu/redingtn/www/netadv/Xinformati.html>
- [WikiBert] Bertrand paradox (probability), Wikipedia. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bertrand_paradox_\(probability\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bertrand_paradox_(probability))

Appendix A:

English Translation of Bertrand's Paradox by chatGPT, October 2025

Translated from Joseph Bertrand's Original French Text

Source

Joseph Bertrand, *Calcul des probabilités*, Gauthier-Villars, Paris, 1889, pp. 4–5. [Bert1889]
Translated from French to English.

Chapter I: The Laws of Chance (Les lois du hasard)

To clarify the necessity of defining the conditions under which one evaluates chances, let us propose a question whose answer seems at first glance to depend on no ambiguous condition. A chord is drawn at random in a circle; what is the probability that it is longer than the side of the equilateral triangle inscribed in this circle? The question seems perfectly clear, and yet it is not. We will see that it can be understood in several ways, and the probability, depending on the interpretation, will have different values.

First Method

Suppose the chord is determined by its two endpoints, chosen at random on the circumference of the circle, both points being drawn independently and with equal probability for all points on the circumference. To find the probability that the chord is longer than the side of the inscribed equilateral triangle, consider the following: fix one endpoint, say point A, and let the second endpoint B vary along the circumference. The chord AB is longer than the side of the triangle if the central angle subtended by AB (with respect to the center of the circle) is between 60° and 120° , or equivalently, if B lies in one of the two arcs of 120° (one on each side of A, excluding the arcs within 60° of A). Since the total circumference is 360° , the favorable arcs total $120^\circ + 120^\circ = 240^\circ$. Thus, the probability that B falls in these arcs is $240^\circ / 360^\circ = 2/3$. However, only half of this probability corresponds to chords longer than the triangle's side, as the other half includes chords shorter due to symmetry. Therefore, the probability is $2/3 \div 2 = 1/3$.

Second Method

Suppose the chord is determined by choosing a radius at random and then selecting a point at random on this radius as the midpoint of the chord, the chord being perpendicular to the radius at this point. The chord's length depends on the distance from the center to the midpoint. Let the circle's radius be r . The side of the inscribed equilateral triangle has length $r\sqrt{3}$. A chord with midpoint at distance x from the center has length $2\sqrt{r^2 - x^2}$. This chord is longer than $r\sqrt{3}$ if $2\sqrt{r^2 - x^2} > r\sqrt{3}$, which simplifies to $x < r/2$. Since the midpoint is chosen uniformly along the radius (from 0 to r), the probability that $x < r/2$ is $(r/2)/r = 1/2$. Thus, the probability is $1/2$.

Third Method

Suppose the chord is determined by choosing a point at random within the circle and drawing the chord through this point, perpendicular to the line from the center to the point. Consider a circle of radius r . The chord is longer than the side of the inscribed equilateral triangle ($r\sqrt{3}$) if the point lies within a concentric circle of radius $r/2$. The area of the circle with radius $r/2$ is $\pi(r/2)^2 = \pi r^2 / 4$, and the area of the full circle is πr^2 . The probability that a randomly chosen point lies within the smaller circle is the ratio of the areas: $(\pi r^2 / 4) / (\pi r^2) = 1/4$. Thus, the probability is $1/4$.

Discussion

These different methods of choosing a random chord by endpoints, by midpoint on a radius, or by a point in the circle yield probabilities of $1/3$, $1/2$, and $1/4$, respectively. The question, though clearly posed, is ambiguous because it does not specify how the chord is chosen. Each method is equally legitimate, yet the results differ. This paradox shows that the Calculus of Probabilities requires a precise definition of the conditions under which chances are evaluated, otherwise the results are indeterminate.
